

EXTENT OF DOING WARM-UP EXERCISES IN PREPARATION FOR PHILIPPINE TRADITIONAL DANCE PERFORMANCES

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 4

Pages: 481-488

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2071

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12786699

Manuscript Accepted: 06-13-2024

Extent of Doing Warm-Up Exercises in Preparation for Philippine Traditional Dance Performances

Domakrayo E. Flechero*, Christine Marie V. Acuba, Lendee Joy C. Awe, Vince Cornelio E. Dela Fuente, Nikko Pop P. Magtortol, Dante M. Orgando Jr., Melanie Chel N. Panerio

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This descriptive quantitative study determined the warm-up exercises and the extent of these exercises of thirty (30) Philippine traditional dance performers of Kulintayaw Performing Artists Collective of General Santos City in preparation for Philippine Traditional Dance performances. The data were gathered using a validated self-made research questionnaire. It was found that the respondents were often doing static and dynamic exercises, with mean scores of 3.41 and 3.48, respectively, which corresponds to a high extent of preparation before performing Philippine traditional dance performances, as reflected in the overall weighted mean of 3.45. Results showed that most respondents performed both static and dynamic exercises, with frequency distributions varying from 23 to 30, which corresponded to often performing different warm-up exercises, respectively. The performers do shoulder stretch, standing shin stretch, quadriceps stretch, jumping jacks, and walking knee hugs more frequently than upper back stretch, adductor stretch, arm circles, lunges, and squats. This means that some exercises were only performed occasionally by the respondents. Performers were encouraged to further improve and do warm-up exercises prior to physical activities, for it enhances their performance in Philippine traditional dance.

Keywords: *dynamic warm-up exercises, Philippine traditional dance, static warm-up exercises*

Introduction

Before traveling, the vehicle is repeatedly idled to warm up its engine and ensure optimal engine performance during the ride. Just like human bodies, people also need to warm up their muscles in order to effectively perform a specific task without causing damage. According to Cronkleton (2019), a time-pressed individual may attempt to reduce or eliminate body warm-up and then proceed directly to physical activity. However, it may increase their chances of getting injuries and muscle strains.

It was widely accepted that body preparations, such as warming up, are essential for optimal performance. According to Walker (2016), in order to maximize a person's potential, professionals must be aware of both the significance and the potential of a well-designed warm-up. Warm-ups are known to both reduce injury risk and improve performance, as well as improve mental and physical readiness for physical activity.

The importance of this study was to highlight factual ideas about warm-up exercises in preparation for dance performances. The warm-up exercise session of Philippine traditional dance performers should be assessed in order to know how they apply these facts about warm-ups to their performances. Adequate warm-up protocols after a physical activity may help individuals' performance, therefore, this study aimed to ascertain the extent to which Philippine traditional performers, particularly the Kulintayaw Performing Artists Collective of General Santos City, warm up before performances. Through this, one can also learn about the various advantages of warming up, such as improving performance ability and preventing injuries.

As present-day cultural dance enthusiasts, they are expected to share their knowledge of traditional dances, and it is presumed that they will be teaching future performers to perform physical activities and dance routines while growing. Because proper warm-up is important and relevant in all physical activities, such as dancing, it is important to understand how people get involved, recognize, and represent the importance of warm-up exercises. Therefore, this research aims to identify the extent to which the Kulintayaw Performing Artists Collective does warm-up exercises in preparation for Philippine traditional dance performances. The lack of information and local research on this subject captivated the researchers' interest and compelled us to seek thoughts on it.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study was to determine the extent of Philippine traditional dance performers doing warm-up exercises in preparation for Philippine Traditional Dance performances. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What are the different warm-up exercises performed by Philippine traditional dance performers?
2. What is the extent of doing warm up exercises in preparation for Philippine traditional dance performances in terms of the following:
 - 2.1. static warm-up exercises; and
 - 2.2. dynamic warm-up exercises?

Literature Review

Philippine Traditional Dances

Traditional dances are a reflection of a society's culture, which has been shaped by its history, ethnography, and folklore. Lewis (2012) defines folk dance as a traditional form of expression that involves recurring patterns of physical movement that link distinctive elements of musical or rhythmic rhythms. He went on to say that although Philippine folk dances are similar to those of other Southeast Asian countries, they are also incredibly diverse and full of history. Filipino folk dances evolved from their indigenous origins into a cultural convergence of the East and the West thanks to the influence of Spanish rule and American culture. According to Aquino (1952), the mother of Philippine dancing, the modern folk dances of the Philippines have an odd fusion of Spanish and Oriental movements. This is how it ought to be. Because of the more than three centuries of contact with Spaniards, their influence may be heard in the music and dances. The dances differ from other Oriental dances in this regard. A Philippine folk dance presentation, according to Namiki (2011), is a collection of regional dances that exhibit Hispanic, European, and other Asian cultural elements that are often put together into a program and turned into a stage production. By combining high art with folklore, modern and traditional, Philippine folk dance, therefore, expresses and embodies a hybrid cultural identity of the Philippines.

The traditional dance of the Philippines varies depending on where you are in the archipelago. According to Namiki (2011), there are five main groups of traditional dances in the Philippines: cordillera dances, dances with influences from the West, or "Maria Clara," dances from the Muslim or Moro people, Lumad dances, and rural or countryside dances.

The majority of dances in Mindanao are rural, Moro, and Lumad dances. Lewis (2012) asserts that a genuine classical tribal dancing form can only be found in the most remote areas. These Muslim and other ethnic groups' pre-Hispanic, non-Christian ceremonial, and folk dances have less formality and organization than the majority of Christian dances. The dances of Islamized populations in the Mindanao and Sulu archipelago, such as the Maranao and Tausug dances, which share moves with adjacent nations like Indonesia and Thailand, are presented by the Moro, according to Namiki (2011). According to Lewis (2012), Singkil is a well-known bamboo and fan-like dance performed by Muslim organizations. In this dance, ladies manipulate scarves or fans while high-stepping between parallel or tic-tac-toe-arranged bamboo poles that are clapping. This dance takes its name from a Maranaw tale about Princess Gandingan, who had to skip deftly from one spot to another as she walked through the forest to avoid stepping on fallen trees and boulders after fairies caused the ground to tremble.

According to Namiki (2011), the Lumad dance genre is relatively new and showcases the dances of indigenous non-Muslim and non-Christian people in Mindanao, including the T'boli, Bagobo, and Bukidnon. The rural or countryside dances showcase the upbeat and playful dances of rural people with dances like "Tinikling" and "Pandango sa Ilaw," which exhibit a distinctive fusion of western and native/local forms of dancing found at a mass level. And according to Lewis (2012), where Spain had a significant influence, the Christian Filipinos' Spanish-style dances can be found in the lowlands. Although non-Christian ceremonies and rituals were forbidden by the Spanish, performances of native dances that had been altered were permitted on holy days. European-influenced dances eventually entered the mix; one such dance is the Polkabal, which blends the polka with the waltz. The Mananguete recreates the manufacture of coconut wine, and the Surtido Cebuano, a sort of square dance with French influences. The two further remaining Filipino dances are the Binasuan Candle Dance and the national folk dance of the Philippines, Tinikling, which is done similarly to the Singkil.

Traditional dancing in the Philippines is diverse. According to Namiki (2011), Philippine folk dance effectively lends visual expression to the country's hybrid identity culture, which is a blend of East and West, by contrasting both Western and Asian cultural heritages coexisting in the Philippines.

Purposes and Effects of Warm-up Exercises

There are empirical ways that can improve dancers' performances. Warm-up exercises can be efficient when it comes to muscle and body preparation for physical activity. It is consistent with the article by McGowan, Pyne, Thompson, and Rattray (2015) that warming up is commonly acknowledged before exercise as an essential way of achieving peak performance. Warming up passively or actively can have similar effects on body temperature, metabolism, the nervous system, and psychology, such as boosting anaerobic metabolism, accelerating oxygen uptake kinetics, and potentiating post-activation. Therefore, warm-up exercises as a preparation for Philippine traditional dance performers' activities are essential for them to secure optimal performance. Having an adequate amount of warm-up exercises may help the performers acquire these benefits.

According to Altalilla and Raiola (2018), the primary purposes of the warm-up are to physiologically prepare individuals for training, prevent muscle injuries, recall technical skills prior to race start, achieve maximum concentration, and achieve psycho-physical activation. This refers to the idea that physiological effects are not the only thing we can expect from warming up, but also psychological ones.

It is congruent with the study by Silva, Neiva, Marques, Izquierdo, and Marinho (2018), which claimed that a warm-up procedure in training is critical in boosting preparation for subsequent effort and maximizing performance. Several preparation tactics have been studied over the years, and recent research has shown that warm-up routines are usually seen as advantageous to performance. Warming

up is a practice conducted before physical or sports performance to prepare the body for the workout and engagement, enhance physical performance and lower the chance of injury (Altalilla & Raiola, 2018).

In addition, both Rogers (2014) and Cronkleton (2019) claimed that a good warm-up exercise lasts up to five to ten minutes, depending on the intensity of the proceeding activity. The more intense the activity, the longer the warm-up.

Altalilla and Raiola's (2018) study on the physiological effects of warm-up exercises found that in order to maximize the activity of the enzymes responsible for energy production, vasodilation, and blood supply to the muscles, which promote nutrient intake and gaseous exchange at active muscles, increased nerve impulses to muscles, improved dross disposal, and an increase in body temperature are all required. Warming up the body is believed to benefit muscular strength, flexibility, laceration resistance, increased connective tissue elasticity inside the muscle, reduced muscle viscosity, an increase in metabolic rate, and the extensibility of soft tissues. Increases in temperature also have a significant positive impact on joint reactivity, mobility, and the rate of strength development in muscles.

Muscle strength can be crucial to dancers' performances. Heating up body muscles can help you achieve strength efficacy during activities. Silva et al. (2018) explain that warm-ups are often designed to raise muscle temperature, allowing for internal changes such as greater blood flow and improved metabolic reactions. As a result, the best warm-up should enable the mover to achieve an optimal muscle temperature range that minimizes fatigue while optimizing performance.

Same argument as to Park, Jung, Park, Lee, Jee, Eun, Cha, and Yoo (2018), which emphasizes that warm-up exercises raise muscle temperature and blood flow, which enhances exercise performance and lowers the risk of tearing muscles and tendons. Stretching enhances joint range of motion and is useful for injury prevention, exercise performance maintenance, and flexibility enhancement.

According to Morrin and Redding (2013), stretching is frequently incorporated into the warm-up routine before engaging in physical activities, particularly dancing, since it is believed to improve performance and reduce injury risk. Dancers must exhibit broad ranges of motion in addition to having power and control. Dancers are believed to be ideal candidates for excessive static stretching (SS) before class or performance because of this particular necessity.

Benefits of Warm-up Exercises to Performers

Participating in dance groups is really risky for individuals because they are exposed to activities that may harm them if they do not conduct any preparatory measures, such as an active warm-up session. This helps the performers take care of themselves while doing performances, avoiding the risks. Park et al. (2018) added that before beginning the primary workout, warm-ups that enhance blood flow to the relevant muscles and raise muscular temperature are conducted for 5 to 15 minutes. By warming up before high-intensity activities, you can lessen your risk of heart problems and damage to the muscles and tendons that can happen when you quickly start them.

It has been mentioned by McGowan et al. (2015) that when an exercise is preceded by a warm-up, performance benefits are typically attributed to processes influenced by temperature. And as cited by McGowan et al. (2015), Asmussen and Bøje (1945), early pioneers of warm-up research, found that "organisms enable them to work more effectively at higher temperatures." It simply says that having the right body temperature before any activity can be a good indicator that a performer may perform well because of its effects.

Silva et al. (2018) emphasized that in addition to elevated body temperature, research has also revealed elevated resting oxygen uptake, a post-activation potentiation (PAP) effect influenced by prior use of the same muscle group, an improved muscle contractile response and consequently the capacity to generate power, less muscle resistance, and psychological effects. McGowan et al. (2015) also claimed that although performance will be hampered by fatigue, including muscle "potentiation" exercises in an active warm-up could enhance performance in the future.

Kobal, Pereira, Kitamura, Paulo, Ramos, Carmo, Roschel, Tricoli, Bishop, and Loturco (2019) stated that having strength and power is essential in many activities. Coaches and researchers are always looking for new and better ways to enhance these skills. The use of resistance exercises with moderate or high loads during warm-up activities for athletes has been suggested to function as a sort of conditioning activity (CA), potentially causing significant improvements in later motor tasks. This process, known as post-activation potentiation (PAP), is thought to be a result of certain physiological and neuromuscular reactions, such as higher rates of motor unit recruitment and enhanced phosphorylation of the regulatory light chains of myosin. Significant increases in muscular tension and, subsequently, strength and power output have been seen as a result of these effects.

McGowan et al. (2015) explained that by increasing ATP turnover and muscle cross-bridge cycling rate, as well as by enhancing muscle fiber functionality and conduction velocity, passively or actively elevating muscles can significantly affect the performance of a subsequent exercise.

It is also congruent with Park et al. (2018), who pointed out that adenosine triphosphate turnover, which supports muscular functions, muscle cross-bridge cycling rate, and oxygen uptake kinetics are all increased during passive and active warm-ups. These findings imply that a rise in muscle temperature during an active warm-up indicates the possibility of enhanced blood flow to the working muscle, consequently enhancing the aerobic contribution to energy metabolism at the start of activity (Altalilla & Raiola, 2018). These effects have a significant impact on exercise performance.

According to Harvard Health Publishing (2020), warming up brings nutrient-rich, oxygen-rich blood to your muscles while increasing your heart rate and breathing rate. An effective warm-up should take five to ten minutes and include exercises for all major muscle groups. Start softly, then ramp up the speed for the best results. Several warm-up regimens include cardiovascular and range-of-motion activities like jumping jacks and lunges. You may do a basic warm-up by strolling in place while gently swinging your arms or even dancing to a few songs if you want.

Upon doing physical activities, a maintained increase in body temperature would be necessary, knowing that an increase in body and muscle temperature is an important component for performance; hence, according to Altalilla and Raiola (2018), it is critical to keep the temperature at an ideal level (about 39°). To do so, the performer must take effective action regarding this. As suggested by Silva et al. (2018), using appropriately planned warm-up tactics and minimizing unnecessary rest periods in the post-warm-up promotes explosive performance. A brief active warm-up approach (10–15 minutes), progressively increasing intensity (50–90% of maximal heart rate), and the use of heated garments shortly after the warm-up to maintain muscle temperature are all recommended. However, for transitions lasting more than 15 minutes (90% of maximum heart rate), a 2-minute vigorous re-warm-up with short-term sprints and hops is recommended. Finally, pairing heated clothes to maintain muscular temperature and completing an active strategy.

Flexibility in an individual's muscles can help address the risk of possible injuries. Park et al. (2018) state that stretching is frequently done to increase the range of motion (ROM) of joints. It is useful for maintaining and improving flexibility and exercise performance, as well as for injury prevention. Therefore, static stretching exercises can also be beneficial for the performers during their physical activities.

Moreover, Park et al. (2018) also highlight that, despite these results, warm-ups have been widely used in modern sports environments because competitive professional athletes and amateur sports club members consider warm-ups a requirement for achieving the highest performance (even in dancing). But on the other hand, Altalilla and Raiola (2018) claim that since the warm-up phase is acknowledged as a chance for movers to psychologically prepare for an impending event by allowing them to concentrate on their task at hand, many of them complete some form of mental preparation prior to the competition tasks. Warming up is used to raise body temperature, but energy expenditure is required, which implies that it should not be expensive; therefore, it is necessary to avoid carrying out too many intense exercises during the warm-up phase.

Based on the evidence in the review of McCrary, Ackermann, and Halaki (2015), an ideal upper body warm-up routine should include a mix of high-load dynamic warm-ups to improve performance and short-duration (60 s) static stretching to improve flexibility. Considering that the previously mentioned connections between flexibility and injury risk may be generalized.

Morrin and Redding (2013) claimed that using static stretching and combined stretching, create significant ROM (Range of Motion) increases were seen. This further supports the compelling evidence that static stretching results in transient increases in ROM. Combination stretching's effects on ROM have not yet been investigated, however, static stretching combined with aerobic exercise has been proven to significantly increase ROM. Because of this, static stretching appears to be a useful component of warm-ups that explicitly attempt to increase ROM.

Morrin and Redding (2013) added that the results of current studies should persuade people to combine dynamic exercise with static stretching instead of relying solely on static stretches as a warm-up technique. They should also direct dance instructors and dancers away from the traditional approach.

These findings and information lead to the conclusion that warm-up exercises greatly influence an individual's performance output, enabling them to physiologically prepare their body for a preceding physical activity. Therefore, a conclusion is drawn that it is important for the Philippine traditional dance performers to have an adequate extent of doing this body-preparation warm-up up exercises to ensure great possibilities of better performance and anticipate fewer injuries during and after the tasks.

Methodology

Participants

Thirty (30) performers of the Kulintayaw Performing Artists Collective of General Santos City were randomly chosen as study respondents. This group is a community-based cultural performing group that helps people develop their skills methodically and thoroughly, preparing them to be active members of society.

They promote varied kinds of Philippine traditional dances that enable performers to learn motor skills, and they will be having events that require actual performances. They actively engage in performing at different events, celebrations, and festivals that require actual performances. In line with this, it is expected for them to conduct physical activities such as performing Philippine traditional dances frequently and consistently, which enables performers to learn motor skills for optimal performance. Therefore, the researchers sought to know the performers' extent of doing warm-up exercises and applying them in their preparation for their performances and used random sampling in choosing the respondents. In line with this, a random sample is meant to be a fair representation of the population as a whole.

Instruments

For the chosen respondents, one instrument was used in this study: a self-made questionnaire that was validated by educational research experts. The instrument was used to collect data, specifically on the extent of warm-up exercises before performing Philippine traditional dances.

Questionnaire. A research questionnaire was used by the researchers in conducting the survey. It is a list of questions designed to assess respondents' extent of doing warm-up exercises in preparation for traditional dance performances. The instrument is in the form of a Likert scale or checklist questionnaire, with the format including 20 questions that are divided into two parts based on the various warm-up exercises respondents perform and the frequency of performing different warm-up exercises, answerable by yes-or-no and with a 5-point rating scale; 5 is always, 4 is often, 3 is sometimes, 2 is rarely, and 1 is never. Thus, the primary goal is to provide significant information about the respondents' extent of doing warm-up exercises in preparation for performing Philippine traditional dances. Research experts validated this instrument and ensured its validity and relevance to the study. The scale used was:

Range	Interpretation	Description
4.21-5.00	Always	I do this exercise as part of my warm-up routine with the extent of 46-60 seconds
3.41-4.20	Often	I do this exercise as part of my warm-up routine with the extent of 31-45 seconds
2.61-3.40	Sometimes	I do this exercise as part of my warm-up routine with the extent of 16-30 seconds
1.81-2.60	Rarely	I do this exercise as part of my warm-up routine with the extent of 1-15 seconds
1.00-1.80	Never	I never do this exercise as part of my warm-up routine

Procedure

The researchers obtained permission from the coordinator of the Kulintayaw Performing Artists Collective of General Santos City to conduct the data collection survey. Following approval, the researchers collaborated with the officers of the said organization and the respondents to notify them of the survey. The researchers distributed a survey questionnaire to performers with a time limit for responses. Following the completion of the survey, the researchers retrieved all of the survey papers. The results of the above-mentioned survey questionnaire assisted the researchers in achieving their goal. In preparation for data analysis and interpretation, all data obtained are tabulated, collected, and statistically calculated.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers ensured that all ethical considerations were followed since it helped them avoid engaging in actions that could implicitly or explicitly abuse or exploit individuals with whom they sought to do research.

Informed Consent was distributed to the respondents in order to make them aware of the evaluation being conducted. Respondents can make an informed decision about whether or not to participate in the evaluation.

Data Privacy was strictly observed as mandated by the Data Privacy Act of 2012. All the personal data of the respondents was secured and kept confidential to protect the fundamental human right to privacy.

Voluntarily Participation of the respondents was highly considered. Researchers provide a way for respondents to participate in the evaluation without feeling pressured.

Gender Sensitivity was valued by the researchers upon conducting the research survey. This study considers the equal rights of any gender of the respondents participating in this scientific work.

Cultural Sensitivity was very well thought of by the researchers towards the target respondents. The researchers respect and understand the cultural contexts of the respondents, which makes this research avoid misunderstanding.

Health and Safety Protocols were strictly followed by the researchers, such as wearing of masks, observing social distancing, and proper sanitation.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Different Warm-up Exercises Performed by Philippine Traditional Dance Performers (n=30)*

<i>In preparation for Philippine traditional dance performances, I do...</i>	<i>Frequency</i>		<i>Positive Percentage</i>
	<i>Yes</i>	<i>No</i>	
Upper back stretch	25	5	83%
Shoulder stretch	30	0	100%
Adductor stretch	25	5	83%
Quadriiceps stretch	29	1	97%
Standing shin stretch	28	2	93%
Jumping jacks	29	1	97%
Walking knee hugs	29	1	97%

Arm circles	25	5	83%
Lunges	23	7	77%
Squats	23	7	77%
Overall Average	26.6	3.4	89%

Table 1 shows the different warm-up exercises performed by Philippine traditional dance performers. Results show that most respondents perform both static (upper back stretch, shoulder stretch, adductor stretch, quadriceps stretch, and standing shin stretch) and dynamic (jumping jacks, walking knee hugs, arm circles, lunges, and squats) exercises in preparation for Philippine traditional performances, with frequency distributions varying from 23 to 30, which corresponds to always performing different warm-up exercises, respectively. The results obtained were consistent with the findings of the Kaufmann, Nelissen, Stubbe, and Gademan (2022) study, which found that 47.4% of ballet dancers consistently warmed up using stretching, technical exercises, strength training, and the barre, whereas 9.4% never warmed up.

Table 2.1. *Static Warm-up Exercises (n=30)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
Upper back stretch	3.20	Sometimes
Shoulder stretch	3.77	Often
Adductor stretch	3.13	Sometimes
Quadriceps stretch	3.53	Often
Standing shin stretch	3.43	Often
Total	3.41	Often

Table 2.1 shows the extent of doing static warm-up exercises. It is found that the respondents were often doing static exercises with total mean score of 3.41 which described their preparation before performing Philippine Traditional folk dances using static exercises. The shoulder stretch, quadriceps stretch, and standing shin stretch were described as warm-up exercises that often used by the performers while both of the upper back stretch and adductor stretch were described as warm-up exercises that sometimes used by the performers. It is congruent to the study of Page (2012) and that proved that static stretching appears to be particularly effective for athletes that require flexibility for their activities (e.g., gymnastics, dance). Static stretching is useful for increasing range of motion. The biggest change in range of motion occurs between 15 and 30 seconds with a static stretch, and it has been suggested that 10 to 30 seconds is adequate for developing flexibility.

Table 2.2. *Dynamic Warm-up Exercises (n=30)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
Jumping jacks	4.03	Often
Walking knee hugs	3.83	Often
Arm circles	3.30	Sometimes
Lunges	3.03	Sometimes
Squats	3.23	Sometimes
Total	3.48	Often

Table 2.2 shows the extent of doing dynamic warm-up exercises. It is found that the respondents were often doing static exercises with a total mean score of 3.48 which described their preparation before performing Philippine Traditional folk dances using dynamic exercises. Both the jumping jacks and walking knee hugs were described as warm-up exercises that were often used by the performers while the arm circles, lunges, and squats were described as warm-up exercises that were sometimes used by the performers. It is congruent with the study of McGowan et al. (2015). Their research provides credence to the idea that a well-structured dynamic warm-up enhances performance in a variety of activities. They added that performance increases after an active warm-up that consists of 4-5 activation sprints/race-pace efforts, post-activation potentiation exercises, or small-sided games after a quick (15 minute) aerobic part.

Table 2.3. *Extent of Doing Warm-up Exercises (n=30)*

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Description
Static Exercise	3.41	Often
Dynamic Exercise	3.48	Often
Total	3.45	Often

Table 2.3 shows the extent of doing warm-up exercises. It is found that the respondents are often doing static and dynamic exercises, with mean scores of 3.41 and 3.48, respectively, which corresponds to a high extent of preparation before performing Philippine traditional folk dances. Taken together, these results show that the respondents have a high level of preparation before performing, as reflected in the overall weighted mean of 3.45. This implies that all the performers prepared themselves for performing Philippine traditional dance performances by combining static and dynamic stretching. It was congruent with the study of Morrin and Redding (2013), and they proved that combined static and dynamic exercise was more efficient at improving balance and vertical jump range in dancing. As a result, it can greatly increase the range of motion measurements before and after stretching. Because of this, their research recommended that a mixed warm-up program made up of static and dynamic stretching be promoted as an efficient warm-up for dancers.

The preceding tables and written paragraphs successfully described the current extent of warm-up exercises performed by Philippine traditional dance performers and identified the warm-up exercises being used. All the questions being sought by the researcher that had been stated in this study's statement of the problem were answered. By means of acquiring unbiased results with the utilization of a validated survey questionnaire, the gathered numerical data was presented and tabulated in accordance with the standards of Holy Trinity College of General Santos City.

Conclusions

Some of the performers were not doing many of the static warm-up exercises. 17% of them do not do the upper back stretch and adductor stretch, 7% do not do the standing shin stretch, and 3% do not do the quadriceps stretch. Therefore, we concluded that some of the performers were lacking in their body preparation prior to the performance in terms of doing static warm-up exercises.

Some of the performers were not doing dynamic warm-up exercises. 23% of them do not do lunges and squats, 17% do not do arm circles, and 3% do not do jumping jacks and walking knee hugs. Therefore, we concluded that some of the performers were lacking in their body preparation prior to the performance in terms of doing dynamic warm-up exercises.

On doing static warm-up exercises, researchers conclude that the respondents do shoulder stretches, standing shin stretches, and quadriceps stretches more frequently than upper back stretches and adductor stretches.

On doing dynamic warm-up exercises, the researchers conclude that respondents do jumping jacks and walking knee hugs more frequently than arm circles, lunges, and squats.

The respondents often do both static and dynamic warm-up exercises; therefore, they have a high rate of body preparation prior to performance. The overall extent of doing warm-up exercises in preparation for Philippine traditional dance performances was concluded to be high.

Performers were encouraged to further improve and do warm-up exercises prior to physical activities, which enhances their performance. An adequate warm-up routine after doing Philippine traditional dance performances may help them optimize their bodies for maximal effort. Hence, the researchers suggested developing the warm-up protocols for the performers;

Some performers who are not used to doing warm-up exercises may understand the static and dynamic warm-up exercises used in preparation of Philippine traditional folk dance so that they will be able to apply them prior to performance. They may read articles, watch videos, or seek professional help to further understand warm-up exercises and may create a suitable warm-up exercise session for them;

Warm-up exercises that were already applied and conducted by professional Philippine traditional dance performers may also be conducted in a classroom setting. Therefore, teachers in dance class subjects such as Physical Education, Bachelor of Culture and Arts Education, and Bachelor of Physical Education may integrate these warm-up exercises before doing performance tasks.

This study may be shared with the Kulintayaw Performing Artists Collective of General Santos City to showcase their proud participation in this study by describing their extent of doing warm-up exercises in reparation for Philippine traditional dance performances.

Future researchers may conduct researches that may further develop this present study. They may also describe the extent of doing warm-up exercises of the performers or athletes on other fields aside from Philippine traditional dancers. They may also develop study assessing the relationship between the specific performers or athletes' extent of doing warm-up exercises and their endurance, performances, or physiological/psychological readiness.

Future researchers may conduct research that may further develop this present study. They may also describe the extent to which the performers or athletes on other fields, aside from Philippine traditional dancers, do warm-up exercises. They may also develop studies assessing the relationship between the specific performers or athletes' extent of doing warm-up exercises and their endurance, performances, or physiological or psychological readiness.

References

- Altalilla, G. & Raiola, G. et al. (2018). Physiological effects of warm-up and problems related to team sports. *Sport Science* 11, 1:p 83-88. <https://www.sposci.com/PDFS/BR1101/SVEE/04%20CL%2015%20GA.pdf>
- Aquino, F. (1952). Philippine Folk Dances. *Journal of the American Association for Health, Physical Education, and Recreation*, 23(10), 10–11. doi:10.1080/23267232.1952.10627588
- Asmussen, E. & Bøje, O. (1945). Body Temperature and Capacity for Work. *Acta Physiologica Scandinavica*, 10(1), 1–22. Doi:10.1111/j.1748-1716.1945.tb00287.x
- Baker, C. (2017). Quantitative research designs: Experimental, quasi-experimental, and descriptive. *Evidence-based practice: An integrative approach to research, administration, and practice*, 155-183.

- Cronkleton, E. (2019). 6 Warmup Exercises to Help Boost Your Workout. Healthline <https://www.healthline.com/health/fitness-exercise/warm-up-exercises#dynamic-warmup>
- Fishbein, M. (2008). Reasoned Action, Theory of. The International Encyclopedia of Communication. doi:10.1002/9781405186407.wbiecr017
- Harvard Health. (2020). Exercise 101: Don't skip the warm-up or cool-down. <https://www.health.harvard.edu/staying-healthy/exercise-101-dont-skip-the-warm-up-or-cool-down>
- Kobal, R., Pereira, L., Kitamura, K., Paulo, A., Ramos, H., Carmo, E., Roschel, H., Tricoli, V., Bishop, C., Loturco, I. (2019). Post-Activation Potentiation: Is there an Optimal Training Volume and Intensity to Induce Improvements in Vertical Jump Ability in Highly-Trained Subjects?. *Journal of Human Kinetics* volume 69/2019, 239-247 DOI: 10.2478/hukin-2019-0016
- Lewis, L. (2012). The Philippine "Hip Hop Stick Dance." *Journal of Physical Education, Recreation & Dance*, 83(1), 17-32. doi:10.1080/07303084.2012.10598705
- McCrary, J. Ackermann, B., & Halaki, M. (2015). A systematic review of the effects of upper body warm-up on performance and injury. *British Journal of Sports Medicine*, 49(14), 935-942. doi:10.1136/bjsports-2014-094228
- McGowan, CJ. Pyne, D. Thompson, K. & Rattray, B. (2015). Warm-Up Strategies for Sport and Exercise: Mechanisms and Applications. *Sports Medicine*, 45(11), 1523-1546. doi:10.1007/s40279-015-0376-x
- Morrin, N. & Redding, E. (2013). Acute effects of warm-up stretch protocols on balance, vertical jump height, and range of motion in dancers. *Journal of Dance Medicine & Science*, 17(1), 34-40. doi: 10.12678/1089-313X.17.1.34
- Namiki, K. (2011). Asian Studies (SPECIAL ISSUE: Cultural Hybridities of the Philippines): Hybridity and National Identity: Different Perspectives of Two National Folk Dance Companies in the Philippines (1st ed., Vol. 47). Asian Center. <https://asj.upd.edu.ph/mediabox/archive/ASJ-47-2011/vol-47-2011-cultural-hybridities-philippines.pdf#page=73>
- Nielsen, M. (1938). Die Regulation der Körpertemperatur bei Muskelarbeit. *Skandinavisches Archiv Für Physiologie*, 79: 193-230. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1748-1716.1938.tb01246.x>
- Page, P. (2012) Current concepts in muscle stretching for exercise and rehabilitation. *Int J Sports Phys Ther*. 2012 Feb;7(1):109-19. PMID: 22319684; PMCID: PMC3273886.
- Park, HK. Jung, MK. Park, E. Lee, CY. Jee, YS. Eun, D. Cha, JY. & Yoo, J. (2018). The effect of warm-ups with stretching on the isokinetic moments of collegiate men. *Journal of Exercise Rehabilitation*, 14(1), 78-82. doi:10.12965/jer.1835210.605.
- Ponto, J. (2015). Understanding and evaluating survey research. *Journal of the Advanced Practitioner in Oncology*, 6(2), 168-171. doi:10.6004/jadpro.2015.6.2.9
- Rogers, D. (2014). Warm Up, Cool Down. American Heart Association. <https://www.heart.org/en/healthy-living/fitness/fitness-basics/warm-up-cool-down>
- Silva, LM., Neiva, HP., Marques, MC., Izquierdo, M., & Marinho DA. (2018). Effects of Warm-Up, Post-Warm-Up, and Re-Warm-Up Strategies on Explosive Efforts in Team Sports: A Systematic Review. *Sports Medicine*. doi:10.1007/s40279-018-0958-5
- Walker, O. (2016). Warm-ups. Science for sports. <https://www.scienceforsport.com/warm-ups/>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Domakrayo E. Flechero

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines

Christine Marie V. Acuba

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines

Lendee Joy C. Awe

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines

Vince Cornelio E. Dela Fuente

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines

Nikko Pop P. Magtortol

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines

Dante M. Orgando Jr.

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines

Melanie Chel N. Panerio, MAEd, LPT

Holy Trinity College of General Santos City – Philippines